

Development of a PVDF Piezo-Film Sensor Array for Unsteady Wall-Pressure Measurements in a Turbulent SBLI

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The implementation of a novel, cost-effective PVDF piezo-film sensor array for unsteady wall-pressure measurements in supersonic flows is introduced. With this type of technique, multiple local pointwise measurements can be taken simultaneously from a single thin foil without disturbing the flow field. The paper presents a detailed explanation of the design of the sensor array and of its signal conditioning system. The sensor array is tested in a turbulent incident shockwave/boundary layer interaction (SBLI) at Mach 2 and validated through favorable comparison with a classical Kulite piezoresistive transducer. The results of unsteady wall-pressure measurements also show good agreement with other SBLI studies already presented in the literature.

Nomenclature

M	=	Mach number	x_0	=	Separation onset location
V	=	Voltage	x_{imp}	=	Inviscid shock impingement point
RMS	=	Root Mean Square value	L_{sep}	=	Separation length
Re_U	=	Freestream unit Reynolds number	L_{int}	=	Interaction length
S	=	Separation Point	Q	=	Generated charge
R	=	Reattachment Point	σ_n	=	Mechanical stress
PVDF	=	Polyvinylidene fluoride	D	=	Charge density
t	=	Thickness	St	=	Strouhal number
E	=	Young's module	ϵ/ϵ_0	=	Relative permittivity
d_{3n}	=	Piezoelectric constant	DAQ	=	Data Acquisition System
δ_0	=	Boundary layer velocity thickness	SG	=	Shock Generator
LES	=	Large Eddy Simulation	BL	=	Boundary Layer
f	=	Frequency	σ^2	=	Variance of the time signal
f_s	=	Sampling Frequency	N	=	Number of Samples

I. Introduction

RECENT interest in supersonic and hypersonic flight have maintained the strong enthusiasm of the research community in understanding the physics of shockwave-boundary layer interactions (SBLI)[1]. A critical aspect of SBLIs is their natural unsteadiness, where the shock wave may oscillate at frequencies significantly lower than the turbulent fluctuations in the incoming boundary layer, particularly when the latter separates due to the strength of the incident shock. This high-amplitude low-frequency unsteadiness can lead to a series of issues like structural failures, panel flutter and self-induced instabilities such as buffet and inlet buzz[2–4]. Even though a wide body of research on SBLIs has been

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Fig. 1 Piezofilm sensor setup.

conducted in the past decades, both numerically and experimentally[5], the driving mechanisms of the low-frequency unsteadiness behaviour is still not fully understood, so that further investigations are required. Furthermore it is evident that, for experimental studies in supersonic or hypersonic wind-tunnel facilities, dynamic sensing devices are required.

The low-frequency unsteadiness in separated SBLIs is readily observed through measurement of wall-pressure fluctuations under the separated shock foot. Most researchers to date have used piezo-resistive pressure transducers (often *XCQ series Kulites*[®]) because of their relatively small size and high-bandwidth[2]. For measurements of spatial wall-pressure correlations, the main drawback of Kulites is the requirement to use several sensors, which may drastically increase the cost of the experimental setup. Another option is to use unsteady pressure-sensitive paint, which has the advantage of providing two-dimensional unsteady pressure fields, though at the expense of complex calibration procedures and lower frequency-response range and signal-to-noise ratio than conventional pressure transducers [6–9].

In the present contribution we introduce an intermediary concept, where local, pointwise measurements may be obtained at many positions on a test surface but without any significant increase of instrumentation cost. This is achieved using PVDF piezofilm sensor arrays, which have already been used in a wide range of applications. For example, Clemente et al. developed a non-invasive blood pressure PVDF based sensor for use in the bio-medical field [10], Dimitrov [11], Arndt [12] and Wang [13] successfully applied piezo-film sensors to cavitation research in the hydraulics field, while Seminara et al. [14] and Kim et al.[15] used PVDF senso arrays in the robotics field to develop tactile sensors. In aerodynamics, Cong et al. showed how a piezoelectric-film sensor array can be used to study the unsteady flow in an axial compressor [16, 17], while Li et al. managed to obtain flow velocity information from pressure fluctuations taken with PVDF sensors [18]. Of particular interest is the work of Nitsche and co-workers applied to a large variety of flow configurations. They employed PVDF arrays for transition investigations[19], shock detection over a transonic airfoil[20], and more generally for a variety of experimental campaigns in supersonic, transonic and low speed wind tunnels[21–23]. In-flight piezo measurement for flow instabilities and unsteadiness were also performed[24–29].

Piezo-film sensors are based on the organic polymer *polyvinylidene fluoride* (PVDF) whose piezoelectric proprieties have been discovered for the first time by Kawai in 1969 [30]. The piezoelectric effect of the material (change in surface-charge caused by mechanical loading of the film) is due to the particular crystalline disposition that the polymer acquires after artificial polarization through a strong electric field (300 kV/cm) under mechanical stretching conditions. PVDF can be extruded into very thin foils down to 9 μm thickness, thus allowing the development of integrated, low-intrusion, flexible systems that do not alter the flow, and the construction of sensing devices which can be adapted to the morphology of the experimental setup. The polymer layer is coated on both sides with a thin layer of metal (Ni-Cu, Ag, Al, Au), so that the 2 faces of the film act as collectors for the charges generated by the external forces through the piezoelectric effect of the PVDF layer. Furthermore, the metal coating layer can be partially etched into custom shapes and patterns keeping only a wanted portion of the metal. In such a way it is possible to form specific active sensing areas with virtually as many sensors as required from a single foil. Figure 1 shows a schematic of the setup of

M	Re_U	δ_0	Shock generator angle	Test section dimensions
2	$12.5 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^{-1}$	7.2 mm	6° - 10°	150 mm x 150 mm

Table 1 Supersonic wind tunnel parameters.[31]

a PVDF sensor, with some example of etched arrays obtained by removing the coating from one side (figure 1b), or from both sides (figure 1c). In figure 1a the signal chain is shown: the application of an external mechanical stress causes a charge build-up over the two faces of the film. The resulting voltage is very low but can be measured by proper conditioning through a charge amplifier. It is important to note that, because of the capacitive behaviour of the PVDF material, charges generated on the two electrodes slowly cancel each other. This implies that this kind of sensor is only capable of detecting pressure fluctuations (AC signal) and not the mean pressure field.

Given the attractive proprieties of PVDF piezo-films, including their relatively low cost, the possibility of installing them on a curved surface, their wide frequency and dynamic ranges with high sensitivity to pressure variations, not to mention their robustness to mechanical stress and external environmental factors, the aim of this work is to design and test a cost-effective, non-invasive, PVDF unsteady-pressure sensor array, to be used in the specific case of turbulent SBLI to address the low-frequency unsteadiness of the separation shock. The present paper will be structured in the following manner: in Section II the experimental setup adopted for this work will be introduced showing the supersonic facility employed in the tests as well as a detailed outline of the sensor designed and built for this study. Section III will then present results of fluctuating pressure measurements obtained with the new PVDF sensor array in an incident shock interaction at Mach 2. Particular emphasis will be put on comparison and validation experiments with a conventional piezo-resistive pressure sensor (Kulite). Finally, the advantages and inconveniences of the new sensor array for SBLI research will be discussed.

II. Experimental Setup

A. Test Facility and Test Case Arrangement

The experimental investigations were carried out in the supersonic wind tunnel at the Chair of Aerodynamics of *Technische Universität Berlin*. An in-depth review of the facility is presented by Rohlfis et al. [31], and a schematic representation is shown in figure 2. The tunnel has continuous indraft operation: the air is sucked in by a centrifugal compressor, driven up to 16000 rpm by a 400 kW electric DC motor. The flow then goes through a heated drying chamber in the basement of the laboratory, and after passing the settling chamber and screens, it enters inside the test section, which is composed of a Mach 2 supersonic nozzle and a shock generator used to create an incident SBLI with the (turbulent) floor boundary layer. The main characteristics of the wind tunnel and test section are presented in table 1.

The flow field of interest is a turbulent shockwave boundary layer interaction created by means of a shock generator

Fig. 2 Schematic representation of the supersonic wind tunnel present at *TU Berlin* with a focus on the turbulent SBLI test section.[31]

Fig. 3 Representation of a separated shockwave-boundary interaction, adapted from [1]. The white circles are representing the positions of the PVDF sensors.

with a deflection angles of 10° . The resulting oblique shock reaches the wind-tunnel floor and interacts with a fully turbulent boundary layer of $\delta_0 = 7.2$ mm thickness. The topology of this type of flow is shown in figure 3: the oblique shockwave, impinging on the turbulent boundary layer, generates a strong adverse pressure gradient. This separates the boundary layer and creates a separation bubble with reversed flow between the *separation point* S and the *reattachment point* R and with a characteristic length L_{sep} . The curvature of the bubble induces converging compression waves in the incoming flow that merge into a *separation shock*, interacting with the incident shock, and forming the characteristic λ -foot of the separated SBLI. Another important parameter to consider for the following investigations is the interaction length L_{int} defined as the distance between the extrapolated impingement point x_{imp} (from inviscid shock theory) and the interaction onset x_0 where the wall pressure starts to rise.

B. Piezofoil Sensor Array

1. Piezofoil Design

For the purpose of this study, commercially available piezofoils were used. The metallised piezoelectric films were obtained from *TE Connectivity*TM[32], they consist of a $110 \mu\text{m}$ thick sheet of PVDF coated on both sides with a few μm of silver ink. The main properties of the film are presented in table 2 [33]. It is important to note that while the frequency and dynamic ranges shown in the table are strictly properties of the material, the actual values of the final sensors depend on the entire signal chain, from the charge amplifier to the DAQ system, as we will discuss later.

As already introduced previously, the working principle of this type of piezoelectric sensor is based on the charge produced inside the semicrystalline structure of the PVDF by an external mechanical stress. The generated charge density D , in absence of an external electrical field, can be expressed as:

$$D = \sum d_{3n} \sigma_{3n} \quad (n = 1, 2, 3) \quad (1)$$

where d_{3n} and σ_{3n} are respectively the piezoelectric constant and the mechanical stress along the direction n , where 1 = length, 2 = width, 3 = thickness. In the present study we are interested in the pressure fluctuation applied on the sensor, hence $n = 3$ (normal stress). Furthermore we assume that the shear stress fluctuations ($n = 2, 3$) can be neglected [34]. So, considering only the 3rd direction and multiplying equation 1 by the active area A , which is the sensitive part of the sensor where the positive and negative electrodes overlap, we obtain the value of the charge Q generated by the sensor:

t	d_{33}	E	ϵ/ϵ_0	Freq. Range	Dynamic Range	T Range
$110 \mu\text{m}$	$33 \times 10^{-12} \text{ C/N}$	$4 \times 10^9 \text{ Pa}$	12	$10^{-3}-10^{10} \text{ Hz}$	$10^{-5}-10^9 \text{ Pa}$	$-40 \text{ to } 80^\circ \text{ C}$

Table 2 Typical characteristics of PVDF piezo-films.[33]

Fig. 4 Piezofilm array experimental setup: (a) exploded view of the final sensor PCB layout; (b) setup for the patterning with the LPKF™ Protomat S63; (c) section view of the PCB layout with the signal (red) and ground (blue) paths; (d) pattern of the proposed sensor array (dimension in mm).

$$D = d_{33}\sigma_{33} \quad \Rightarrow \quad Q = DA = d_{33}\sigma_{33}A \quad (2)$$

From equation 2 evaluations on the spatial resolution can be made: ideally the smallest possible sensor size should be chosen for the best resolution, however a sensing area too small wouldn't produce enough charges for a good signal to noise ratio. Furthermore, the size of the sensor has also an influence on the frequency response, because the high frequency range of the spectrum is generated by the smallest fluid structures, so if the sensor size is larger than the flow structures it will filter their contribution and the high frequency response will be attenuated.

The pattern adopted is shown in figure 4d. The array is composed of 18 circular sensors, with a diameter spanning from 2.5 mm to 4.5 mm, arranged in a 6x3 matrix with 10 mm pitch between consecutive sensing points along the streamwise direction. To create the chosen pattern, the metal coating is removed with the help of a LPKF™ Protomat S63 machine, a CNC mill for microstructuring applications with a resolution of 0.5 µm. So the pattern is created by mechanically engraving the metal layer of the piezofilm with the machine spindle rotating up to 60 000 rpm. To obtain cleaner contours the foil is covered with a protective layer which is removed in a later stage with lithography techniques. The sensor production process has been carried out in the laboratory of Hochschule für Technik und Wirtschaft Berlin and the described setup is shown in figure 4b.

After the etching process the challenge of finding the proper connection setup arises. This step is critical, since the appropriate interface between the metal coatings of the piezofilm and the signal conditioning system is needed in order to prevent unwanted noises and signal degradation. Various ways of creating connections from the PVDF's electrodes exist. Penetrative techniques, such as piercing, riveting or crimping the foil are widely used commercially, but cannot be used easily in an array setup, since they would alter the shape of the film spoiling its low profile. On the other hand, non-penetrative techniques like conductive glues, cold soldering or conductive tapes, can be employed more conveniently and are used for this study. Specifically, the patterned PVDF film is connected to a PCB via a special conductive tape, which is only conductive through the thickness direction (3M™ 9703). This arrangement provides a stable low-impedance connection of the sensors, without altering its shape or damaging the coating. Figure 4a shows the connection setup with the conductive tape and PCB technique. The final assembly is composed by a multilayered

Op-Amp	C_f	R_f	R_i	C_p	f_L
TLC-272	100 pF	100 M Ω	56 Ω	10 pF	15.9 Hz

Table 3 Charge amplifier design parameters.

Fig. 5 Electrical circuit of a charge amplifier and its frequency response.[35]

structure formed by:

- a rigid PCB block with passthrough contacts, patterned in the same way as the piezo array, and soldered wires;
- 3M™ 9703 z-conductive tape;
- the patterned PVDF film and an aluminum foil with the same thickness;
- 3M™ 9703 z-conductive tape;
- aluminum foil covering the full sensor area.

The last two layers (tape and aluminum foil) are needed to capture the charge from the upper ground electrode while maintaining as flat a surface as possible. Furthermore the aluminum layer also acts as an electromagnetic shield. For a better understanding, the signal and ground paths of the setup are shown in figure 4c, which represents the section view of the full sandwich structure.

The final sensor is mounted flush to the test section floor, and wires are soldered on the bottom of the PCB in order to connect the array to the signal conditioning system.

2. Signal Conditioning and Acquisition System

The output voltage measured directly from the piezo sensors is only a few mV, so a proper amplification system is needed to obtain a signal readable by the acquisition system with a good SNR. Given the high impedance of the PVDF, a high-impedance amplifier is required, and for this work a charge amplifier has been chosen. The electrical circuit of a typical charge amplifier, as well as its frequency response, are reported in figure 5. As we can see the main advantage of using such amplifier is that the output voltage depends only on the feedback capacitance C_f (with the relation $V_o = -Q/C_f$) and not on that of the cable (C_c) or sensor (C_p), allowing the use of longer cables and a minimization of charge leakage [33]. For the best performance of our PVDF sensors the charge amplifier was designed with the components shown in table 3. The operational amplifier at the heart of the system is the *Texas Instruments*™ TLC-272, a CMOS single supply amplifier with low offset voltage drift, high input impedance and low noise behaviour. The feedback capacitor C_f balances the charges injected into the negative Op-Amp input. The resistor R_f prevents the amplifier from drifting into saturation, by slowly bleeding the charge off the feedback capacitor. The values of C_f and R_f set the low cutoff frequency of the charge amplifier with the relation $f_L = \frac{1}{2\pi R_f C_f}$, which in our case lead to a cutoff frequency of $f_L = 15.9$ Hz. The resistor R_i provides electrostatic discharge (ESD) protection and, combined with the sensor (C_p) and cable (C_c) capacitance, set the high cutoff frequency $f_H = \frac{1}{2\pi R_i (C_p + C_c)}$ which is in the MHz range, so well beyond the frequency range we are interested in.[35]

The signal acquisition is carried out by means of a *National Instruments*™ NI-USB 6353 data acquisition card, in order to obtain PSDs up to 100 kHz a sample rate of $f_s = 200$ kHz for $N = 200000$ samples with a resulting period of $T = N/f_s = 1$ s was used.

Fig. 6 Time traces of the 18 sensors from the piezofoil array.

III. Results

In the following section the results obtained with the proposed sensor are introduced. The sensor arrangement under the SBLI flow is represented in figure 3:

- Position 1: in proximity of the interaction onset location x_0 ;
- Position 2: under the λ -shock foot;
- Position 3-6: under the separation bubble.

In figure 6 are plotted the time signals acquired for the full 18 positions of the piezo array, each row correspond to one of the 6 positions just introduced and the columns to the different sized sensors as showed in figure 4d (1a-6a = $\varnothing 4.5$ mm, 1b-6b = $\varnothing 3.5$ mm, 1c-6c = $\varnothing 2.5$ mm). We can immediately see the amplitude variation between the differently sized sensors and also along the streamwise direction. Indeed the streamwise distribution of the signal's RMS can be used as mean for detecting the shock foot position. From figure 7b it is clear how the RMS of the signal starts to rise after the sensor located under the shock foot (position 2). Larger sensors (positions 1a-6a) have a higher signal amplitude but also, as explained earlier, a lower spatial resolution and frequency range.

Figure 6 shows the excellent capability of the piezo array for simultaneous surface unsteady-pressure measurements, but unfortunately due to a DAQ limitation we were only capable of measuring the full array at a sample rate of $f_s = 40$ kHz. Therefore for the following frequency domain analysis we will use only the central column of the array (positions 1b-6b) with the acquisition parameter introduced before ($f_s = 200$ kHz, $N = 200000$, $T = N/f_s = 1$ s).

The time traces are transformed with *Welch's method* (20 Hanning windows with 75% overlap) to obtain the Power spectral densities in figure 7a. From the PSD spectra it's not so easy to deduce the characteristics of the flow unsteadiness. Thus the normalized *premultiplied PSD* ($PSD(f) * f/\sigma^2$) was evaluated with the frequency normalized trough the *Strouhal number* $St_L = fL_{sep}/u_\infty$ and the streamwise length with the separation length as $X^* = (x - x_0)/L_{sep}$.

Fig. 7 Time and frequency domain results from PVDF-array measurements: (a) PSD spectra of the acquired signal for every streamwise position ($\varnothing 3.5$ mm); (b) streamwise distribution of the signal RMS values; (c) 3D plot of the premultiplied PSD spectra distribution along x dimension; (d) 2D surface plot of the premultiplied PSD distribution.

Fig. 8 Comparison between Piezofoil and Kulite.

Fig. 9 a) Turbulent SBLI LES simulation from [36]. b) Comparison between Piezofoil (in colors) and LES.

A comparison between the $f \cdot PSD$ obtained with the novel PVDF sensors and a state of the art Kulite pressure transducer, are shown in figure 8. The Kulite used is the fast response piezoresistive transducer *XCQ-062* whose signal was fed into a low-pass filter with a cut-off frequency of $f_L = 100$ kHz. The Kulite was mounted flush with the floor of the test section and the acquisitions were taken sequentially for positions corresponding to the 1st, 2nd, 4th and 6th of the PVDF array. The signal was acquired with the same DAQ as the piezofilm, and the data processed with the same Welch’s method parameters. The results show how the newly developed piezofilm sensors are able to match the Kulite data quite precisely, and to capture the unsteady characteristics accurately.

The normalized premultiplied PSD distribution, obtained from the piezofilm array at positions 1b-6b, are shown in figure 7c and 7d. From the plots it is possible to obtain interesting information about the energy content at various frequencies and locations of the SBLI. We can see the high St_L peak generated by the incoming boundary layer for the 1st position of the sensor ($X^* = -0.2$). Moving downstream, in correspondence with the separation onset location x_0 and under the λ -shock foot ($X^* = 0$), the majority of the energy is located between $St_L = 0.03 - 0.05$ range. This is the low-frequency signature of the separated SBLI, in good agreement with the literature [2, 36–38]. Under the separation bubble and inside the interaction ($X^* = 0.4 - 0.8$) most of the energy is located between $St_L = 0.5 - 1$. This region is generally associated with vortex structures developing in the separated shear layer.[39]

In conclusion, to further evaluate the accuracy of the measurements obtained with the new sensor array, the premultiplied PSD distribution was compared qualitatively with the LES results of Agostini et al.[36] in a turbulent SBLI configuration similar to the one investigated herein. The comparison is shown in figure 9, where the $f \cdot PSD$ distribution showed in figure 7d has been superimposed over the one obtained by LES. Despite the fact that the experimental domain is much smaller in comparison to the computational one, there is a good match between the two distributions for what concerns the position, in frequency and location, of the most energetic part of the spectra. Indeed we can clearly identify the three zones mentioned above: the incoming BL, the low-frequency region and the medium-frequency ones, which are present at the same locations in both the simulation and the experiments.

IV. Conclusion

A novel unsteady wall-pressure sensor array, based on piezoelectric flexible films, has been developed and tested in a turbulent SBLI configuration in the supersonic wind tunnel of TU-Berlin. The first prototypes have been manufactured with the help of Hochschule für Technik und Wirtschaft Berlin with mechanical milling and lithography techniques. The proposed array is composed of 18 circular sensors obtained from a single Ag coated PVDF foil of 100 μm thickness. The sensor array offers a good spatial resolution and minimal flow intrusiveness, all at a fraction of the cost of an equivalent system with common dynamic pressure transducers such as Kulites. The flow investigated is a turbulent SBLI obtained with a 10° shock generator in a continuous supersonic wind tunnel at Mach 2. The capability of the array for multi-point surface measurement was showed by acquiring the signal of the 18 sensor simultaneously, unfortunately, due to a limitation of the acquisition system, the frequency domain investigations were carried out only with 6 out of 18 sensors (the DAQ system will be upgraded for future works). The premultiplied PSDs obtained with the new sensor array compared favorably with reference measurements taken with a state of the art Kulite pressure sensor, thus confirming the validity of the proposed sensor array for unsteady wall pressure measurements. Indeed the obtained $f \cdot PSD$ distributions showed a good agreement with the results found in literature, both experimentally and numerically, with the low-frequency unsteadiness region under the separation shock foot ($X^* = 0$) characterized by a Strouhal range of $St = 0.03 - 0.05$. This first results support the idea of using this type of sensors for unsteadiness investigations where good spatial resolution and low intrusiveness is needed, such as in SBLI studies. Further work will be carried out in order to determine the optimal sensor shape and size for our specific test case and to improve the performances and the robustness of the sensor. Indeed, due to the small thickness of the foils and the harsh supersonic environment of the SBLI, the piezofilm production and especially the packaging of the final sensor represent a complex challenge.

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